

The FAIR-Decide Framework components

The FAIR-Decide framework contains three primary modules for handling decision making on FAIRification, described as follows:

- **Module 1: Structure of FAIRification decision**

This component of the tool helps users structure their FAIRification decisions. Its purpose is to guide users throughout the identification of FAIRification goals and scope as well as stakeholders involved. As a decision maker becomes more involved in the FAIRification process, the approach should be flexible enough to allow for adjustments. This module requires having a general knowledge and understanding of the dataset of interest.

- **Module 2: Assessment of benefit factors**

The benefit factors are: (1) the reusability of data assets and (2) cost savings.

This module instructs users to assess benefit factors using the benefit scale, which is of a five-point Likert design intended to specify the level of beneficence derived from each factor: 1 = *very low benefit*, 2 = *low benefit*, 3 = *moderate benefit*, 4 = *high benefit* and 5 = *very high benefit* (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The benefit scale

- **Module 3: Assessment of cost factors**

The cost factors are: (1) legal and ethical considerations, (2) dataset characteristics and (3) required resources.

This module instructs users to assess cost factors using the cost scale, which is of a five-point Likert design intended to specify the level of costs incurred in relation to each factor: 1 = *very low cost*, 2 = *low cost*, 3 = *moderate cost*, 4 = *high cost* and 5 = *very high cost* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The cost scale

The FAIR-Decide framework’s general features, logical process and components have been delineated, but an issue worth considering is that such details point to complex implementation and the need for more practical steps to craft a pilot product (e.g. a tool or model) that can be tested and evaluated by pharmaceutical professionals in R&D units. The succeeding sections explain the implementation strategy aimed at converting this framework into a more practical integrated tool.

Implementation for the FAIR-Decide tool

This section describes the actual implementation of the FAIR-Decide framework for its development into an integrated tool that supports the evaluation of the benefits and costs associated with FAIRification.

- **Tool selection**

The integrated tool was developed using Qualtrics XM¹, a powerful web-based questionnaire and a service provided by the University of Manchester’s Information Governance Office (IGO)². The development of the tool and specific functions in each stage

1 <https://www.qualtrics.com>

2 <https://www.staffnet.manchester.ac.uk>

entailed several phases. Here is the link for the FAIR-Decide tool:

https://www.qualtrics.manchester.ac.uk/ife/form/SV_b1vL8dggymfAz4

The input of the tool

This development began with the creation of a project in the selected software (The FAIR-Decide tool) and the subsequent generation of several web pages attached to the project as follow:

1- Landing page: A user guide

The landing page was the first such component created that provides information and guidance for users in effectively using the tool. This information covers the purpose of the tool, the assessment flow, an overview of the framework and the expected duration of assessment (Figure 3).

The FAIR-Decide tool for the FAIRification process in pharmaceutical R&D

This tool is aimed at helping decision makers in pharmaceutical R&D assess the potential outcome of retrospective FAIRification based on cost-benefit analysis principles. The tool informs the aforementioned stakeholders about whether FAIRifying existing data is worth the cost of the investment and helps them prioritise datasets accordingly.

Assessment flow

- Assessment starts with general information intended to structure the FAIRification decision.
- This stage involves answering a few questions about your role, the roles of other stakeholders who are involved in this process, the data of interest and what type it is, the goals of FAIRification and its scope.
- Next, you need to address questions about cost and benefit factors, and the majority of these entail scoring the factors and identifying their weights to reflect their importance in the FAIRification decision.
- The weighted sum of these factors is then calculated to provide scores on the expected costs and benefits of FAIRification.
- Additional information and guidance on how to properly answer each of the questions are provided (accessible by clicking on the 'i' icon).
- The assessment ends with the generation of a decision file, which you can save as a PDF file or share with your colleagues.

Framework overview

Expected duration of assessment

You need 20 to 30 minutes to complete the assessment, depending on your familiarity with the subject and issues covered.

[Go to the decision structure module](#)

Figure 3: The landing page for the FAIR-Decide tool

2- Module 1 page: Structure of decision making on FAIRification

This module was developed to allow users to structure their decisions, as requested by the participants. To reiterate, although this information is not directly used in analysis, the approach directs users' attention to problems and prospective concerns. Figure 4 presents a screenshot of the corresponding page.

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Module 1: Structure of decision making on FAIRification

This component of the tool helps you structure the FAIRification decision. Its goal is to guide you through the identification of the goals and scope of FAIRification and other stakeholders involved. The process should be sufficiently flexible to allow for changes as you becomes increasingly immersed in the FAIRification process.

Note: This module requires having a general knowledge and understanding of the dataset of interest.

Identify your role. i

R&D strategy lead	Data manager	IT professional	Laboratory head
Associate director	Data steward	Researcher	Data scientist
Head of data strategy	Data provider	Legal consultant	Other

Identify the project name. i

Select the dataset type. i

Figure 4: The module 1 page

As shown in Figure 4, a decision maker is asked to identify their role to help determine user focus (e.g. technical, business, data or legal focus). The user is then instructed to identify the project name or title to ascertain the existing data associated with the project so that users can refer to such initiatives by their assigned labels. After this, the user is directed to select a dataset type from a list that contains data commonly used in drug discovery and development (R&D). If their data is not on the list, the user can write their data types manually (other data type). To make sure that the tool covers a comprehensive array of data types, we populated the list with EDAM ontology topics³ (topics - bioscience-biomedical, science- medicine research and development). This list encompasses acceptable topics in the domain but is not an exhaustive catalogue of issues related to pharmaceutical R&D data taxonomy, which was lacking in public research and privately known for each company.

Next, the user is asked to specify the goal of the FAIRification process and define its scope. The identification of scope enables users to ascertain what part of a dataset needs to be FAIRified. Lastly, the user is asked to identify the roles of other stakeholders involved in the FAIRification decision-making process to specify which decisions are made by particular members of a team.

To facilitate the completion of assessment, we added an information guide to most questions, which is accessible by pressing the information buttons (*i*) located next to a sentence.

3- Module 2 page: Assessment of benefit factors

This module is intended to identify the benefits expected from FAIRification (Appendix B listed all questions related to this assessments). CBA assessment typically commences with an evaluation of costs followed by benefits, but to ease this procedure for users, as discussed with the UX researcher who provided assistance during the development process. The

³ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/EDAM>

recommendation was to initiate the assessment of the value of FAIRification in a logical manner.

Accordingly, a brief definition of each factor, the rating scale and the series of questions through which scores are to be given by users begins the process. More importantly, as this tool applies the WSM for scoring, users should assign a weight to each factor to, as declared earlier, reflect the importance of this factor in the final decision. To allow for flexibility, the researcher made several options available in terms of response choices ('yes', 'no', 'requires further investigations', 'not applicable to my role' and 'I do not know') (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The module 2 page

4- Module 3 page: Assessment of cost factors

This part of the tool is designed to assess the cost factors associated with FAIRification (Appendix A listed all questions related to this assessments). It follows a flow similar to that of the previous module but concentrates on cost assessments. Note that this section is longer

than the benefit assessment because of the various factors affecting the cost of FAIRification (Table 1) . Figure 6 shows a screenshot of this module.

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Module 3: Assessment of cost factors

Cost factors are the set of factors or indicators that influence the costs associated with retrospective FAIRification. These factors are: (1) legal and ethical considerations, (2) characteristics of the dataset, and (3) the resources required.

Cost factors

Please assess the following cost factors using the cost scale. ⓘ

First factor: Ethical and legal considerations

Figure 6: The module 3 page

Table 1: Cost- Benefit Factors with number of associated questions.

	Factor	Sub-factor	Number of questions
Cost	Ethical and legal considerations	Access Rights	8
		Ethics Compliance	3
	Dataset characteristics	Data Quality and Management	8
		Data Volume and Dimensionality	3
	Required resources	Human resources	5
		Technical resources	2
Benefit	Reusability of data assets	Relevance and importance	4
		Uniqueness and novelty	3
	Cost savings	Future research	1
		Rerunning experiments	1

Tool analysis (normalisation and calculation)

As mentioned earlier, this tool uses the WSM in assessing cost and benefit factors, each accompanied with a five-point scale. Carrying out normalisation is essential to provide an accurate output value. This procedure involved developing categories for each assessment (cost and benefit factors) using the built-in scoring function of Qualtrics (Figure 7).

How relevant is this data to the current project?

Clear

Irrelevant Slightly relevant Moderately relevant Very relevant Extremely relevant

Relevance to the current project 1 2 3 4 5

How important is this data to your business?

Clear

Not at all important Slightly important Moderately important Very important Extremely important

Importance in business 1 2 3 4 5

How likely is that the company using this data gain a competitive advantage?

Clear

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

Gaining a competitive advantage 1 2 3 4 5

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.: Normalisation

Similarly, a mathematical calculation using the WSM was developed so that codes are not repeated for cost and benefit assessments. This was not a straightforward process and required significant effort to implement because it is not a built-in function. It entailed technical support from the Qualtrics support centre and a software adviser who helped develop such a calculation function for the WSM. The calculation was developed using embedded data in the software and by modifying the JavaScript (Figure 8).

The image displays seven stacked panels, each titled "Set Embedded Data:". Each panel contains the following information:

- Score Name:** A label followed by "Number".
- Formula:** An equals sign followed by a JSON-style formula: `{ round (gr://SC_.../WeightedMean , 2) }`.
- Action:** A blue link "Add a New Field".
- Buttons:** A row of buttons: "Add Below", "Move", "Duplicate", "Add From Contacts", "Options", and "Delete".

The scores and their corresponding formulas are:

- Relevance and importance score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_9Sr2s7I8AgWA6TI/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Uniqueness and novelty score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_9oxxBF91wUqi5E/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Future research score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_3miOfDg1F29KCO/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Re-running of experiments score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_bIMiPkrWa8ir09w/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Overall benefit score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_cO3i3nkZJV8aUm/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Access right score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_821zN6Y2Rn838Io/WeightedMean , 2) }`
- Ethics compliance score Number = `{ round (gr://SC_eVvLwEpjZZATot8/WeightedMean , 2) }`

Figure 8: Embedded data for scoring

The output of the tool (assessment report)

The tool provides an assessment report for users to view their assessment results on the costs and benefits of FAIRification (Figure 9 and 10).

Cost-benefit Assessment Report

Date: 23 Mar 2022

Time: 3:33 AM

Part 1: FAIRification Decision Structure

A- General information to structure the FAIRification decision.

Your Role	Roles of other Stakeholders	The Project Name	The Data Type
-----------	-----------------------------	------------------	---------------

B- The goals of FAIRification and its scope.

FAIRification Goal	FAIRification Scope
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Part 2: The Cost-benefit analysis summary

A- The overall scores for cost and benefit factors.

The overall cost score of this FAIRification process is which indicates a **very low cost**.

The overall benefit score of this FAIRification process is which indicates a **very low benefit**.

Figure 9: Part of an assessment report

To Save or Print this report [Save or Print this Report](#)

There is an option to **email** you the summary of your response. If you are interested, please enter your email and then press **Send a response summary** at the end of this page.

Note: We will not keep a record of this email address.

[Send a response summary](#)

Figure 10: Saving, printing and emailing reports

Appendix A

The costs assessment questions

The University of Manchester

Module 3: Assessment of cost factors

Cost factors are the set of factors or indicators that influence the costs associated with retrospective FAIRification. These factors are: (1) legal and ethical considerations, (2) characteristics of the dataset, and (3) the resources required.

Cost factors

Please assess the following cost factors using the cost scale.

First factor: Ethical and legal considerations

This factor revolves around the legal and ethical issues related to performing FAIRification. It includes the legal right to access data and ethical compliance in retrospectively carrying out FAIRification.

What is the importance or weight of the ethical and legal aspects in your FAIRification decision?ⁱ

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance/ weight of legal and ethical aspects	<input type="radio"/>				

1.A Access right ⁱ

Can you access this data?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>
Requires further investigation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Not applicable to my role	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know	<input type="checkbox"/>

Which part of the data can you access?

	The whole set of an original dataset	A subset of the dataset	An aggregated dataset	A subset of the aggregated dataset	None
Data availability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which part of the metadata can you access?

	The whole set of metadata	A subset of the metadata	An aggregated metadata	A subset of the aggregated metadata	None
Metadata availability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you need to have authorisation to access this data?

	It is accessible	It is accessible, but Low admin control of access	It is accessible, but high admin control of access	Difficult or high-cost licensing model	No access
Authorisation process	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you know where this data is stored?

Central database

Individual computers

Paper-based documentation

Other

Is it important to know who owns the data?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Do you know who owns this data?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

How likely will legal issues related to this data be resolved?

	Extremely likely	Somewhat likely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Extremely unlikely
Resolution of legal issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Justify your selection in this section.

2.B Ethics compliance i

Are there any compliance issues relating to reusing this data?

Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>
No	<input type="checkbox"/>
Requires further investigation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Not applicable to my role	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know	<input type="checkbox"/>

Are there likely to be any GDPR issues relating to this data? i

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Is there any need for anonymisation?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

How likely is that anonymisation will affect data accuracy?

	Extremely accurate	Very accurate	Moderately accurate	Slightly accurate	Not accurate at all
Data accuracy after anonymisation	<input type="radio"/>				

Justify your selection in this section.

Second factor: Dataset characteristics

Dataset characteristics represent the current state of a dataset in terms of data quality, management and volume.

What is the importance or weight of the dataset characteristics in your FAIRification decision?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance/ weight of dataset characteristics	<input type="radio"/>				

2.A Data quality and management

How can you describe the quality of the data?

	Excellent	Good	Acceptable	Poor	Very poor
Data quality	<input type="radio"/>				

2.A.1 Machine readability i

How can you describe the machine readability of the data?

	DB system with API	DB system without API	Delimited files/XML/JSON	Text file/word/PDF	Paper/scan
Machine readability of data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2.A.2 Metadata availability i

How complete is the existing metadata?

	Complete for all data	Sparse for all data	Very little for all data	Absent for a subset of data	Absent for all data
Completeness of metadata	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Does the available metadata comply with community standards?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

2.A.3 Identifiers i

Does the data have a persistent and unique identifier?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

2.A.4 Documentation i

Is this data accompanied with a data management plan (DMP)?

	DMP + FAIR	DMP	DMP without compliance	Incomplete DMP	No DMP
Obtaining a DMP	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2.A.5 Ontologies i

Which types of ontologies are associated with this data?

Internal ontologies

External ontologies

Mix of internal and external ontologies

Application ontologies

None

Other

Will the FAIRified data require ontologies?

	Extremely likely	Somewhat likely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Extremely unlikely
Ontologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Justify your selection in this section.

2.B Data volume and dimensionality

How can you describe the size of the dataset?

	Byte (B)	kilobyte (KB)	Megabyte (MB)	Gigabyte (GB)	Terabyte (TB)
Dataset size unit	<input type="radio"/>				

Can you estimate the number of files or the number of web pages associated with this data?

How many megabytes or gigabytes does this data constitute?

Justify your selection in this section.

Third factor: Required resources

The resource requirement factor involves the human and technical resources needed to carry out FAIRification. Human resources include having skilled personnel and efficiently managing these resources (e.g. role assignment). Technical resources pertain to the availability of the internal IT applications needed to perform FAIRification or the need for an external tool.

What is the importance or weight of the required resources in your FAIRification decision?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance/ weight of required resources	<input type="radio"/>				

3.A Human resources

Do you have access to the originators of the data?

Yes	<input type="text"/>
No	<input type="text"/>
Requires further investigation	<input type="text"/>
Not applicable to my role	<input type="text"/>
I do not know	<input type="text"/>

How likely are you to have in-house experts available to perform FAIRification?

	Extremely likely	Somewhat likely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Extremely unlikely
Availability of in-house expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How long would it take to FAIRify this data?

	A very short time (A Few hours)	A short time (A few days)	A medium time (A few weeks)	A long time (A few months)	A very long time (A year)
Estimated time required	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you need to recruit more staff to perform FAIRification?

	Definitely not	Probably not	Might or might not	Probably yes	Definitely yes
New staff recruitment	<input type="radio"/>				

Justify your selection in this section.

3.B Technical resources i

To the best of your knowledge, are your internal IT applications compatible with one another? i

Yes
No
Requires further investigation
<input type="text"/>
Not applicable to my role
<input type="text"/>
I do not know

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Is there a need for external tools?

	Definitely not	Probably not	Might or might not	Probably yes	Definitely yes
Necessity of external tools	<input type="radio"/>				

Justify your selection in this section.

This is the end of the cost assessment. The next page shows the cost-benefit assessment report (output in the form of PDF), and displays the calculated scores for each factor (the cost-benefit chart).

[Go to the cost-benefit assessment report](#)

Appendix B

The benefits assessment questions

Module 2: Assessment of benefit factors

Benefit factors can be defined as the value proposition for performing FAIRification. In other words, what value can be gained from this process? This value can be seen from two dimensions: (1) the reusability of data assets and (2) cost savings.

Benefit factors

Please assess the following benefit factors using the benefit scale. i

First factor: Reusability of data assets

The reusability of data assets at scale is the main benefit obtained from implementing FAIR principles in pharmaceutical R&D. This process is useful in generating value from data assets by enabling companies to use the data in deriving novel scientific insights.

What is the importance or weight of the reusability of data assets in your FAIRification decision?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance/ weight of data reusability	<input type="radio"/>				

1.A Relevance and importance

Is this data relevant to the current project?

Yes	<input type="text"/>
No	<input type="text"/>
Requires further investigation	<input type="text"/>
Not applicable to my role	<input type="text"/>
I do not know	<input type="text"/>

How important is this data to your business?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance in business	<input type="radio"/>				

How likely is it that the company using this data will gain a competitive advantage?

	Extremely unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat likely	Extremely likely
Gaining a competitive advantage	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Will you be able to reuse this data if it is in the FAIR format? i

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Justify your selection in this section.

1.B Uniqueness and novelty i

Is this data unique?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Do other projects in the company depend on this data?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

How likely will the data address area(s) of high societal impact?

	Extremely unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat likely	Extremely likely
Societal value	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How likely will this data affect a priority area?

	Very low effect	Low effect	Average effect	High effect	Very high effect
Cross-domain effects	<input type="radio"/>				

Justify your selection in this section.

Second factor: Cost savings

Aligning data with FAIR principles can have a positive financial effect on pharmaceutical organisations, as it would enable them to maximise value from data assets. The availability of relevant data can prevent the duplication of experiments, which in turn, lowers costs and accelerates timelines across the R&D pipeline.

What is the importance or weight of cost savings in your FAIRification decision?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Importance/ weight of cost savings	<input type="radio"/>				

2.A Future research

Can this data be used as input for future research?

Yes	<input type="text"/>
No	<input type="text"/>
Requires further investigation	<input type="text"/>
Not applicable to my role	<input type="text"/>
I do not know	<input type="text"/>

Justify your selection in this section.

2.B Rerunning of experiments i

Do you expect that FAIRification can save on costs in the re-creation of data at a later time?

Yes

No

Requires further investigation

Not applicable to my role

I do not know

Justify your selection in this section.

This is the end of the benefit assessment. The next page features the cost assessment.

[Go to the costs assessment](#)